
91. Cerium and the Galaxy infall history

IN THIS ESSAY, I will bring together two of the remarkable new avenues of research into the formation and evolution of our Galaxy that are being opened up by Gaia. And I will discuss the consistency between them – a consistency that only Nature could conjure up!

I will need to explain what cerium is, why it is relevant to astronomy, how it is measured by Gaia, and what its occurrence tells us about the formation of our Galaxy.

CERIUM, atomic number 58, despite its classification as one of the rare-Earth elements, is not at all rare in the Earth's crust; at 66 ppm, it lies (just) behind copper, and is far more abundant than, say, lead or tin. Its two most commonly occurring isotopes are ^{140}Ce , produced in both the s- and r-processes (slow- and rapid-neutron capture) of stellar nucleosynthesis, and ^{142}Ce , produced only in the r-process (e.g. Lawler et al. 2009).

While the formation sites of the r-process elements are still somewhat uncertain (and may include the cataclysmic merging of neutron stars, or of neutron star-black hole binaries), those of the s-process elements are better (if still imperfectly) understood. Of interest to us here, the 'main' s-process elements such as Ce and Nd are produced in low- and intermediate-mass asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars, making use of neutrons produced by the $^{13}\text{C}(\alpha, n)^{16}\text{O}$ reaction.

Meanwhile, massive stars ($8 - 10M_{\odot}$) are mostly responsible for the 'weak' s-process, producing Sr, Y, and Zr. Here, the neutrons are mainly provided by the $^{22}\text{Ne}(\alpha, n)^{25}\text{Mg}$ reaction in convective He-burning cores and C-burning shells. Low-metallicity, low-mass AGB stars can produce the elements of the third peak (such as Pb) through the 'strong' s-process.

As a result, studying the Ce content of stars across the Galaxy provides a probe of these different production sites. Various studies over the past decade have typically found flat trends of $[\text{Ce}/\text{Fe}]$ versus $[\text{M}/\text{H}]$, perhaps with a small decreasing trend for large $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ values.

Others have suggested a decreasing cerium abundances with age, at least up to about 8 Gyr, both for open clusters and field stars, and an increasing abundance with age for stars older than 8 Gyr.

THE RECENT Gaia Third Data Release (DR3, June 2022) contains a homogeneous analysis of millions of high-quality stellar spectra, obtained by the radial velocity spectrometer on Gaia, reduced and calibrated on the ground within the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC) by Coordination Unit 6, and analysed by the GSP-Spec module of Coordination Unit 8, responsible for the source classification and 'parameterisation' (Recio-Blanco et al. 2022).

As I have described in essay #89, this leads to abundance estimates for up to 13 individual elements in the atmospheres of several million stars, and the possibility for unprecedented chemical mapping of our Galaxy.

And among the abundances derived in GSP-Spec are three of the heavy-elements produced by these neutron-capture processes: Ce, Zr and Nd. In common with all Gaia abundances, these are estimated by comparing the mean observed spectra with an extensive grid of synthetic spectra covering a wide range of stellar atmospheric parameters, and with varying abundances.

A FIRST ANALYSIS of the Ce abundance data has been made by Contursi et al. (2022). Among the 5.5 million stars parameterised by GSP-Spec, 103 948 have a derived cerium abundance. Selection of a high-quality subset according to the flags provided, their resulting sample comprises about 30 000 Ce abundances distributed in the disk and halo components.

The example shown here, centred on the triplet of Ce II lines around 851.375 nm, has a derived Ce abundance compared to iron, $[\text{Ce}/\text{Fe}] = 0.26^{+0.12}_{-0.08}$ dex.

EQUIPPED WITH this sample of almost 30 000 stars with known cerium abundances, the next step is to use the surface gravities determined by the Gaia classification and parameterisation process to establish their nature, and the distances and proper motions provided by Gaia to examine their dependencies on location or kinematics within the Galaxy.

From the former, Contursi et al. (2022) first established that the sample is mainly composed of stars with $\log(g) < 3.5$, that is both red giant branch and asymptotic giant branch stars.

From the astrometry, they found that the closest, being more Ce-poor, more metal-rich, and concentrated within ± 500 pc from the Galactic plane, probably belong to the thin disk population. Stars with higher Ce abundances are at the same time generally metal-poor, and preferentially located at larger distances from the Sun, and at larger distances from the Galactic plane.

These hints are confirmed by their kinematic behaviour: this diagram of Ce abundance with respect to metallicity, colour-coded by the eccentricity of their Galactic

orbits, shows that stars with higher metallicity and low Ce abundance are on more circular orbits typical of thin disk stars, while those with higher Ce abundances are on more eccentric orbits, and so unlikely to belong to the thin disk population.

MORE DETAILED examination of their orbital angular momentum also reveals a small number of lower angular momentum halo stars. And, interestingly, eleven of these stars are associated with previously identified halo substructures, notably the Helmi (2), Thamnos (2), and Enceladus (7) streams. The data was also used to map out the $[Ce/Fe]$ gradient as a function of Galactic radius, and the vertical gradient as a function of the distance from the Galactic plane.

The fascinating thing about these distributions of cerium throughout our Galaxy is that they provide direct support to the latest models describing the chemical evolution of our Galaxy. Let me explain.

I MUST STEP BACK to mention the recent ‘two-infall’ model of Spitoni et al. (2021), designed to reproduce the Apache Point Observatory Galactic Evolution Experiment project (APOGEE DR16) results of $[X/Fe]$ versus $[M/H]$ abundance ratios (where X stands for various α -elements in the solar neighbourhood). That work concluded that high- and low- α sequence stars were formed by two independent episodes of gal infall.

Things got more complicated with Gaia DR3, when Recio-Blanco et al. (2022) identified the presence of young metal-poor stars with low $[\alpha/Fe]$ values. Spitoni et al. (2022) then showed that this low- α population itself can be modelled by two sequential infall episodes, resulting in a total of three discrete infall events.

IN MORE DETAIL, Spitoni et al. concluded that their data could be well reproduced by a ‘three-infall’ Galactic chemical evolution model. The first event, the high- α infall, had an accretion timescale of 0.103 Gyr. The second, termed low- α part I, had an accretion timescale of 4.110 Gyr, and with a delay between the first and second of 4.085 Gyr. The third, low- α part II, had an accretion timescale of 0.150 Gyr, and with a delay between the second and third of 11 Gyr, started some 2.7 Gyr ago.

And, importantly, the model is consistent with the latest cerium results from Gaia which, in the process, independently confirms the quality and reliability of the Gaia DR3 astrophysical parameter determination!

AT THE END of this summary of one of many aspects of ‘Galactic archaeology’ that is being revolutionised by the Gaia data, I’d like to make a few observations.

The first is to recall the difficult days when one of the many tasks I was juggling as Project Scientist was to convince senior ESA management of the merits of including the radial velocity spectrometer (the counter-argument being that ESA does not fly experiments that can be conducted on the ground). I feel ever more vindicated!

The second is to emphasise the huge effort invested by Gaia scientists in optimising all aspects of the satellite payload, including the radial velocity instrument, two decades ago. This was matched by the remarkable expertise of the industrial prime contractor, Airbus Defence & Space, in its design and construction, and by the teams carrying out the data processing on the ground today (and in particular here, those in CU6 and CU8).

Finally, I continue to be awed by the staggering complexity of Nature, in assembling a vast and unimaginably puzzling system that is so hospitable for life. And, indeed, in humanity’s triumphal success in comprehending all that Nature has created... especially as aided by huge numbers of accurate star positions from Gaia!